

ANALYZING THE GENERALIZABILITY OF DEEP CONTEXTUALIZED
LANGUAGE REPRESENTATIONS FOR TEXT CLASSIFICATION

by

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LANGUAGE REPRESENTATIONS FOR TEXT CLASSIFICATION

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ABSTRACT

ANALYZING THE GENERALIZABILITY OF DEEP CONTEXTUALIZED LANGUAGE REPRESENTATIONS FOR TEXT CLASSIFICATION

This study evaluates the robustness of two state-of-the-art deep contextual language representations, namely ELMo and DistilBERT on supervised learning of binary protest news classification and sentiment analysis of product reviews. A “cross-context” setting is enabled using test sets that are distinct from the training data. Specifically, in the news classification task, the models are developed on local news from India and tested on the local news from China. In the sentiment analysis task, the models are trained on Movie Reviews and tested on customer reviews. This comparison is aimed at exploring the limits of the representative power of today’s Natural Language Processing systems on the path to the systems that are generalizable to real-life scenarios. The models are fine-tuned and fed into a Feed-Forward Neural Network and a Bidirectional Long Short Term Memory network. Multinomial Naive Bayes and Linear Support Vector Machine are used as traditional baselines. The results show that DistilBERT is significantly better than ELMo on generalizing to the cross-context setting. ELMo is observed to be significantly more robust to the cross-context test data than both baselines. On the other hand, the baselines performed comparably well to ELMo when the training data and test data are subsets of same corpus (no cross-context). DistilBERT is also found to be 82% smaller and 77% faster than ELMo. The results suggest that DistilBERT can transfer generic semantic knowledge to other domains better than ELMo. DistilBERT is also favorable in incorporating into real-life systems for it requires a smaller computational training budget. When generalization is not the utmost preference and test domain is similar to the training domain, the traditional ML algorithms can still be considered as more economic alternatives to deep language representations.

ÖZET

DOĞAL DİL İŞLEMEDE BAĞLAM ODAKLI DERİN ÖĞRENME YÖNTEMLERİNİN TRANSFER KAPASİTESİNİN METİN SINIFLANDIRMASI PROBLEMİ ÜZERİNDEN İNCELENMESİ

Bu çalışma ELMo ve DistilBERT adındaki bağlamsal ve derin doğal dil sistemlerini protesto haber metni ve kullanıcı yorumlarının ikili sınıflandırılması olmak üzere iki farklı senaryo üzerinden kıyaslamaktadır. Asıl amaç, bu modern sistemlerin birbirinden çok farklı girdileri modellemedeki başarısını ölçmek, bu sayede doğal dil işlemeyi hedef alan sistemlerin gerçek hayattaki kaynak çeşitliliğine ne kadar iyi adapte olabildiğine ışık tutmaktır. Bu amaçla, modeller eğitilirken ve başarımı ölçülürken bağlamca ayrışan veri kümeleri kullanılmıştır. Sözelimi, ilk senaryo için Hindistan ve Çin'in yerel gazete haberlerinden, ikinci senaryo için ise sinema filmleri ve teknolojik cihazlara yapılan kullanıcı yorumlarından faydalanılmıştır. ELMo ve DistilBERT kullanılarak üretilen kelime vektörleri, biri ileriye doğru, diğeri özyineli olmak üzere iki farklı sinir ağına verilmiştir. Daha basit ve bağlamsal olmayan Çokterimli Naif Bayes Sınıflandırıcısı ve Doğrusal Destek Vektör Makinesinin sonuçları temel alınmıştır. Sonuçta, DistilBERT'in ELMo'ya kıyasla, bu iki senaryoda, farklı test ortamlarına daha dayanıklı olduğu, üstüne %82 daha küçük ve %77 daha hızlı olduğu görülmüştür. ELMo ise, yine, farklı bağlama geçişte, iki temel algorithmadan daha başarılı olmuştur. Buradan yola çıkarak, DistilBERT'in dilin genellenebilir anlamsal özelliklerini daha iyi öğrendiği ve gerçek-zamanlı ve bellek kaynağı bakımından sınırlı bütçelerde ELMo'dan daha kullanışlı olduğu yargısına varılabilir. Öte yandan, genellenebilirliğin gözetilmediği, test verisinin eğitim verisine benzediği durumlarda Naif Bayes gibi daha basit ve ekonomik algoritmalar derin sinir ağlarına alternatifler olarak tercih edilebilir.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Natural Language Processing (NLP) has been a promising research area for decades, and it has been living its golden years so far with the rise of Neural Networks in Machine Learning (ML). With the world becoming interconnected more and more, gathering data and setting up the environment has never been this easy. And many different approaches to understand natural languages are proposed and proved effective.

Natural Language Processing is a research area to build computational systems that can interpret the meaning of natural language input in various forms. Understanding a language input, especially if a human is a native speaker, is a trivial process for humans, which continuously takes place on the background of everyday life. But teaching machines to do so is equally hard since this requires humans to break the very process into pieces, and how language acquisition is realized is still a debated question [1].

As the ultimate task is to build a reasonably well language model [2], researchers treated this ultimate goal by dividing it into tasks and attacking each of them separately. There are various NLP tasks, that can be grouped under two main categories: syntactic (eg. part of speech tagging) and semantic (eg. sentiment analysis) tasks. These categories are not mutually exclusive that many tasks fall under both, for the meaning is something revealed by structure and semantics combined. Studying the NLP tasks separately comes handy in which it makes it possible to treat the language understanding problem on different levels of input: token-level (eg. named entity recognition), sentence-level (eg. textual entailment), and document-level (eg. anaphora resolution).

A challenge the NLP community faces today is to leverage NLP systems from a well-maintained test environment to more realistic scenarios with full of dynamism and diversity [2] [3]. Accuracy and speed are the first criteria that might be naturally ex-

pected from a real-life system. But at the same time, an NLP system should generalize well to data coming from diverse sources differing in time and space.

One natural way of imposing robustness to diversity is to create systems using large and diverse data. But this brings yet another challenge, that is, collecting a big task-specific corpus. Even a sufficiently big corpus is available, algorithms may not fully distill the information in the data. Also, even if the gold standard, an offline data set could fail to provide time-dynamic information.

Supervised learning schemes using Neural Networks have long been appreciated as an effective way of modeling data across many fields of study, as they eliminate feature engineering and provide a solid way of tackling various NLP tasks. But the success of Neural Network models is still bound to the quality of labeled task-specific training data.

Creating high-quality labeled data is a difficult job that requires domain-specific expert knowledge and lots of time is spent on the quality assessment before launching the data for use. This makes annotation a painful and time-consuming process. Getting through the same process for every other NLP task does not scale in long term solutions.

The quest of building generalizable systems that are robust and scalable to real-life scenarios in an effective way made the NLP community investigate if they can build task-agnostic models in an unsupervised manner to represent generic syntactic and semantic knowledge of a language. One of the solutions is to create one big universal language representation and use it as the initialization point for any NLP task.

The data preparation bottleneck made the NLP community seek to utilize unlabeled data more. Semi-supervised and self-supervised learning are the products of this quest aimed at incorporating unsupervised language representation techniques more effectively into supervised tasks.

One example of unsupervised language representations is the famous `word2vec`

[4], which creates continuous word vectors for each word in the vocabulary derived from a large corpus in a fully unsupervised manner by utilizing context information regarding the neighboring words. `word2vec` creates fixed vectors to each unique word in the vocabulary. In this sense, it lacks representing the dynamism of the word meaning that changes depending on the enclosing context.

The contextualization notion which was yet unable to fully flourish would be the key to create universal language representations that can handle rich syntactic and semantic space of real-life language usage. In this respect, in the last couple of years, several deep contextual neural architectures are proposed and proved surprisingly well on a diverse range of downstream NLP tasks [5] [6] [7].

These new-generation models (eg. ELMo [5], DistilBERT [8]) attack the generalization problem by building task-agnostic universal language representations in an unsupervised manner to represent generic syntactic and semantic knowledge of a language, to be then fine-tuned for any NLP task. Recent studies validated that with little fine-tuning data, these representations get results competing with supervised task-specific models on many domains [5] [6].

Contextual representations are successful on a diverse set of NLP tasks, suggesting that they capture generally useful and divergent linguistic information. There is still much to do to understand the true capacity of these representations. Exploring the true limits of what these networks offer is the key to understand how to build next-generation systems and much excitingly, digging into these models might shed light on general language understanding phenomena itself on a cognitive level [9] [10]. For this reason, exhaustive evaluation and interpretation studies are needed to be performed on as many different data and task sets as possible.

This study is conducted to contribute to the extrinsic evaluation of the robustness of these representations by testing them on a cross-context data, where the tools are developed on a data from a source country and tested on a target country [3].

More specifically, this study compares internal vector representations of ELMo and DistilBERT on binary protest news classification (PC) and sentiment analysis (SA) of product reviews.

A “cross-context” setting is enabled using test sets that are distinct from the training data. Specifically, in the news classification task, the models are developed on local news from India and tested on the local news from China. In SA, the models are trained on Movie Reviews and tested on customer reviews. A simpler setting will be referred to as “null context” where the models are tested on a subset of the corpora from which the training data sets originate (India and MR test sets).

Using data from different countries makes it possible to create a cross-context setting between training and test phase, which is to use test data that is distinct from both fine-tuning and pretraining data.

This study methodologically deviates from the previous work on assessing the generalizability by using a new socio-political and local news data set other than heavily used data sets. Second, the evaluation is done on a cross-context data (China and CR test sets), without any domain adaptation.

This study asks the following questions:

- (i) How robust are ELMo and DistilBERT in the cross-context text classification?
- (ii) Are contextual representations better in the cross-context than much smaller and faster traditional baselines?
- (iii) Which one is more scalable in terms of model size and training time: ELMo or DistilBERT?

This study draws the following conclusions:

- (i) DistilBERT is more robust than ELMo in the cross-context.
- (ii) Both ELMo and DistilBERT outperform the baselines (Multinomial Naive Bayes

and Linear Support Vector Machine) in generalizing to the cross-context.

- (iii) DistilBERT is more efficient than ELMo with 30% smaller size and on average of the two tasks, 80% faster training time.
- (iv) Traditional methods like MNB and LSVM can still compete with contextual embeddings when training and test data do not differ very much.

As the remaining parts of this study, Section 2 outlines the related work, Section 3 and 4 introduce the tasks and the data sets, Section 5 describes the experimental setup, Section 6 reports the experiment results, Section 7 discusses the results, Section 8 retrospects on what is learnt, and finally Section 9 discourses on the possible improvements and the future work.

2. RELATED WORK

This section gives general information about the strengths and weaknesses of various word representations and language representation techniques in the order of their proposition time. Then the previous work that is focusing on understanding the generalization capacity of the contextual language representations is overviewed.

2.1. Word vectors in transfer learning scheme

Inspired by the success of transfer learning using ImageNet in computer vision, research seeking to build generalizable ML systems has gained attention in recent years of the NLP field. Collobert et al. [11] built a generic model trained using a large amount of unlabeled text data for language modeling task to capture internal representations to be then used for various supervised NLP tasks to reduce reliance on apriori task-specific NLP knowledge.

Then emerged two popular procedures, named Continuous Bag of Words (CBOW) and Skip-Gram models, both to create a language model that computes distributed and continuous word representations from the Google News 6B data set [12]. The former predicts current word based on the context without utilizing word order information, the latter predicts surrounding words both from history and the future based on the current word by maximizing the average log probability of occurrence of context words. Unlike standard Bag of Words, CBOW uses continuous word vectors. These models first learn continuous word vectors in a simple model in an unsupervised manner and then use them to train an N-gram language model. These new log-linear models can capture subtle sense relations between words that previous Feed-Forward Neural Network (FFNN) and Recurrent Neural Network (RNN) based models miss out as they create high dimensional word vectors by training with larger data sets with much lower computational complexity.

As an example of what CBOW and Skip-gram are capable of considering the word

analogy task of finding the word similar to “Germany” in the same sense “sushi” is similar to “Japan”. To achieve this task, first, a vector representation is computed by the operations $V(\text{sushi}) - V(\text{Japan}) + V(\text{Germany})$, then by using cosine similarity, the word with the vector closest to the calculated vector is returned as the answer, which becomes surprisingly the word “bratwurst”.

It is shown that both Skip-gram and CBOW outperform other previous word representations on both semantic and syntactic relationship tasks, where Skip-gram being better than CBOW in semantic relationship tasks. CBOW is trained much faster and can learn frequent words better but it tends to neglect rare words when predicting the word from context, which is a problem handled more chiefly by design in Skip-Gram, which takes word and context pairs as output candidates without causing a race between rare and frequent words [12].

The revolutionary `word2vec` [4] is developed an extension to Skip-gram vectors to create higher quality word vectors by subsampling of the frequent words to alleviate imbalance between rare and frequent words, at the same time speeding up training between 2X and 10X with the help of Negative sampling which is the simplified variant of Noise Contrastive Estimation as an alternative to hierarchical softmax. With `word2vec` creating phrase representations is also made possible, enabling additive compositionality that uncover non-obvious relations such as $V(\text{Russia}) + V(\text{river}) = V(\text{Volga river})$. It is also illustrated that `word2vec` finds more fine-grained relationships between words and phrases than prior word representations [11], also surpassing their performance with a huge margin, requiring a much smaller (a month versus a day) training time [4].

GloVe [13], standing for “global vectors for word representation”, won its well-deserved place as a word representation as effective as `word2vec` yet with much more simpler and faster training procedure that is realized on non-zero entries of a global word co-occurrence matrix with the training objective of learning word vectors so that their dot products are equal to the logarithm of their co-occurrence. In this sense, GloVe attempts, like `word2vec` does, to capture nuance relationships that cannot

simply be represented by a single scalar such as cosine similarity distance between a pair of vectors. Without using word order and with a much faster training schedule, GloVe achieves to attain matching and exceeding scores of Skip-gram and CBOW algorithms on word analogy, word similarity and named entity recognition tasks.

Skip-gram model is adapted to sentence level by Skip Thought vectors [14], which is an encoder model trained on learning generic sentence representations. This encoder than can be frozen and used off-the-shelf in a diverse set of NLP tasks including semantic-relatedness, paraphrase detection, image-sentence ranking, and various classification tasks. Skip thought vectors are an attempt to create robust representations in an unsupervised manner to give freedom in the face of the bottleneck of task-specific supervised training.

Last but not least, Bojanowski et al. [15] use character N-grams to create word vectors to handle unknown and rare words and to also incorporate morphological information to the word representations.

2.2. Contextualized language representations

One of the first attempts to contextualize pretrained word vectors is CoVe [16], standing for “context vectors”, to create shared representations for NLP models with the help of an encoder which is a 2-layer bidirectional Long Short Term Memory network (BiLSTM) pretrained on Machine Translation (MT) task. CoVe is inspired by how transfer learning is applied in computer vision by incorporating an ImageNet model to any other computer vision tasks and mimics this process by replacing ImageNet-Convolutional Neural Network pair with MT-LSTM pair.

The prodigy transformer model [17], solely using attention mechanism, succeeded in outperforming prior sequence transduction models on machine translation tasks which were also relying on convolutions and recurrence relations. The transformer reduces training time by allowing parallelization of computations and generalizes well to other tasks such as constituency parsing with limited training data, and also produces

more interpretable models.

Focusing on enhancing universality on the text classification task, text classification fine-tuning scheme called ULMFiT [18], short for “universal language model fine-tuning”, was proposed that consists of unsupervised pretraining of a generic LSTM-based language model on a large unlabelled data and then transferring knowledge learned by that generic model by supervised fine-tuning on the text classification task.

Radford et al. [7] pinpoint that LSTM restricts the prediction ability to short-range, thus adapts a transformer-based model to the scheme proposed by [18], and evaluates it on a wider range of tasks including natural language inference, paraphrase detection, and story completion.

It is shown further in [7] that a language model that is trained on a large data set (WikiText) performs well across many diverse sets of tasks without the need for explicit supervision and their biggest transformer model named GPT-2 achieved state-of-the-art results on 7 out of 8 tested language modeling data sets in a zero-shot setting.

ELMo [5], short for “Embeddings from Language Models”, is one of the most effective contextual word representation models (Peters, 2018), which is a feature-based word representation aimed at capturing word polysemy within context along with syntactic and semantic characteristics by averaging internal states of a deep bidirectional language model (BiLM) with learned weights (scalar-mixing).

Then BERT [6], standing for “Bidirectional Encoder Representations from Transformers”, emerges with an extraordinary success across many token and sentence level tasks in the traditional NLP pipeline including part-of-speech tagging, co-reference resolution, dependency labeling, etc.—with small multi-layer perceptron (MLP) models and without substantial task-specific architectural modifications. BERT owes its success to incorporating bidirectionality to the transformer model trained on large unlabelled data with the masked language modeling (MLM) objective. Unlike `word2vec`, it learns a context-sensitive representation of a word’s instance within a sentence, by tak-

ing the weighted combination of single attention heads, word order, and word position information.

The bidirectionality is made possible by using MLM as the pretraining objective, in which random words from both left and right context are masked and the model is supposed to find the vocabulary id of the masked words. The vocabulary used in BERT is fixed-sized but it consists of subword units called WordPiece instead of full words in a dictionary. That enables the dismantling of input tokens by WordPiece tokenization and thus the handling of unknown words.

After the success of BERT, many variants emerged such as DistilBERT [8], creating a smaller version of BERT with knowledge distillation; ALBERT [19], shrinking BERT by parameter reduction techniques; RoBERTa [20], optimizing pretraining scheme of BERT for better downstream task performance; XLNet [21], highlighting usage of dependency between masked positions; ERNIE [22], incorporating knowledge graphs to BERT; SciBERT [23], pretraining BERT on scientific text; BioBERT [24] pretraining BERT for biomedicine domain.

DistilBERT [8], which is one of the contextual representations focused on this study along with ELMo [5], is built by leveraging knowledge distillation during pretraining of BERT that is 40% smaller and 60% faster for restricted training budgets and yet attains 97% of BERT’s language understanding capabilities.

2.3. Evaluating generalizability

The evaluation studies before this work are generally designed around a diverse set of downstream tasks to understand knowledge transfer capacity on multiple levels of language input being token, sentence, and document-level [6] [25] [26]. The performance is assessed when taken as fixed feature vectors or when the pretrained parameters are further tuned for the tasks at hand [27]. Ablation studies are also conducted to uncover layer-wise capabilities and effectiveness of different components of the models [25]. Some work focused on how to tune these pretrained representations ef-

fectively on sentence and phrase-level text classification [28], named entity recognition, natural language inference, paraphrase detection [27] to serve as a guide for the NLP practitioner. [18] proposed a set of parameter tuning techniques specifically to leverage text classification performance of pretrained language models. Han et al. [29] applied unsupervised domain adaptation by further pretraining contextual representations on MLM on the target domain. [26] observed that contextual embeddings substantially improve over traditional baselines on learning the syntactic structure of text but that there is only a small improvement in learning semantics on token and sentence level tasks.

2.4. Evaluation on multiple contexts

This thesis study is yet another evaluation study that makes a comparison between two of these representations, namely, ELMo and DistilBERT. But this time, the evaluation is done on part of a recently proposed task set that is realized around a recently proposed news data set: classifying protest news on local news data sets consisting of multiple sentences and coming from different country sources [3], a cross-country evaluation setting is realized by testing a model on a news text coming from a different country than the training data [3].

2.5. Computational text analysis on contentious politics

Automating the analysis of text in social science studies is of increasing interest for various reasons. Integrating ML methods with hand labeling can serve as a validation mechanism for human annotations while it also can accelerate the exhaustive analysis of the huge amount of data.

Especially in the case of large-scale studies with a very generic sociological hypothesis to assess, it becomes crucial to gather lots of local information from a diverse set of sources spanning different countries and time [30] [31]. Manually labeling each new data gets infeasible in terms of time and effort. Automating the labeling process, apart from saving many human hours of labeling, can also help standardize annotation

procedure by automating most of it by enforcing outputs learned from part of the gold standard data.

Prior work that attempts to automate event coding largely relies on domain-specific rules and keywords that become ineffective outside the targeted domain. Even in a single domain continuous dictionary update is required that itself can become a burden and create inconsistencies.

ML methods reduce manual labor dedicated to event coding and eliminate dependence on rules. Neural network-based ML methods, in addition, eliminates most of the feature engineering process. These advantages made researchers turn to automation based on supervision by ML. But one drawback of supervised learning is that it requires lots of labeled data. This poses an ironic contradiction with the ultimate goal of automating information extraction from text, which is the very reason why researchers appeal to ML in the first place.

The way out of this vicious circle can be found in building generalizable ML systems that can be continuously reused regardless of limitations brought by domain. Also, that kind of a system can play the role of a feedback loop on training-evaluation cycle that provides sufficient dynamism to incorporate new labeled data from different sources much faster.

2.6. Cross-context protest news text analysis

A task set [3] was proposed to collect protest event information from news texts recently to create systems that learn transferable information to extract relevant information from multiple countries with the ultimate motivation to create tools to enable comparative sociology and political studies on social protest phenomena. The task set consists of three tasks: news articles classification, event sentence detection, and event information extraction.

A cross-context setting is realized by providing annotated news from India as

train and test sets, and an additional test set that consists of news from China.

In this study, only the first task of the shared task is taken as the probing task for comparison. In this respect, the robustness of ELMo and DistilBERT are evaluated on the binary classification of cross-context protest news articles.

The three tasks mentioned above are realized in the CLEF-2019 Lab ProtestNews on Extracting Protests from News [32] [33] in the context of generalizable natural language processing [3]. From the results gathered from 12 teams, it was observed that Neural Networks obtained the best results and a significant drop in cross-country performance is observed on the news from China [34]. The best performing model on average of null and cross-context trained a BiLSTM with `fastText` [35] [36] embeddings on a multitask learning objective [37]. Safaya et al. [38] attained the smallest score drop between null and cross-contexts using BiGRU and `word2vec`. Another study utilized ELMo with a Fully connected multi layer Neural Network, reaching comparable results [39].

2.7. Sentiment Analysis

Sentiment analysis is a frequently studied classification task. The Movie Reviews (MR) and customer reviews (CR) are a couple of exhaustively used data sets for this task. Zhao et al. as shown in Table 2.1, Zhao et al. [40] attained the highest accuracy scores 83.1 on MR via feeding 50-dimensional `word2vec` embeddings to Adasent, a self-adaptive hierarchical sentence representation. InferSent [41], a sentence representation that is learned by supervised training on SNLI, a Natural Language Inference data [42], achieved the best result of 86.3 accuracy on CR [43]. Logeswaran et al. [44] achieved accuracy scores of 82.4 for MR and 86.0 for CR by training a multi-channel system consisting of two bi-directional RNNs fed by one fixed and one tunable pretrained word vector representation. These results are followed by skip-thought vectors [14], FastSent, a distributed sentence representation learned from unlabeled data [45], `fastText` [36] and GloVe [13] embeddings [43]. Note that these results are obtained by direct supervision on the tasks by 10-fold cross validation. But due

to time limitations, this study uses a single fold of custom training, development, and test splits. As another difference, here CR results are obtained by zero-shot transfer without any usage of the CR corpus.

model	MR	CR
Zhao et al. [40]	83.1	86.1
Conneau et al. [41]	81.1	86.3
Logeswaran et al. [44]	82.4	86

Table 2.1. Sentiment analysis previous work results.

3. TASKS

The transfer capacity of ELMo and DistilBERT are explored under the light of two distinct text classification tasks, each realized under a cross-context. One is a document-level binary text classification task that is to classify English news articles from local newspapers of India and China [3]. The other is to classify sentence-level Rotten Tomatoes movie [46] and customer reviews [47].

3.1. Protest news classification

For the probing task, two test sets are used: one coming from same corpus as train data (null context), the other coming from a different corpus (cross-context).

The task was designed as an auxiliary task for a currently active research project [3], whose main motivation is to automate creating news corpus from diverse sources to enable a comparative political and sociological study. Integrating computational linguistics techniques into the pipeline of social studies can considerably accelerate the collection of relevant data. It also enables verification for manual data labeling as a continuous feedback loop. Humanity studies can benefit as much from automation in data collection and analysis [3] [48]. Although, an efficient collection of vast data must be combined with effective labeling. Automation tools must be capable of a certain level of generalization ability to data coming from many different countries, cultures, and eras. Instead of relying on completely domain-specific rules and features, it must be able to also learn generic linguistic features and transfer to new data fast. Otherwise, scalability becomes an issue when incorporating each new data set into the research pipeline.

A shared task set was accordingly organized to address the challenge of building NLP tools that are generalizable to different test data [3]. Namely, CLEF-2019 Lab ProtestNews on Extracting Protests from News was composed of three levels of news classification tasks: News articles classification, event sentence detection, and event

information extraction. A cross-country evaluation setting was realized by training a model on local newspapers of India and testing the model on local newspapers of China. This thesis study borrows the data and the first task setting (news articles classification) as it is.

In this sense, this thesis study differs from the previous work by enforcing a cross-context testing scenario to see how the models generalize to a zero-shot cross-context test data.

3.2. Sentiment analysis

The second task is the orientation prediction of opinion sentences. Specifically, user reviews on the Internet are marked as “positive” or “negative”. The models are trained on MR data, tested on sentence-level MR data [46] in the null context, on sentence-level CR data [47] in the cross-context.

Both sentiment data sets were exhaustively used earlier [14] [40] [41] [43] [44] [45]. But in none of these studies a cross-context setting is realized. They obtained the result via direct supervision on the target tasks. That is one reason why the results of these work and this thesis study are not comparable. Another factor preventing comparison is that these studies apply 10-fold cross-validation to the data. But due to time limitations, this study uses a single fold of custom training, development, and test splits.

4. DATA

In this study two distinct data sets are used for either task: India and China news articles for PC [3], Movie Reviews [46] and customer reviews [47] for SA. For both tasks, the null context data splits abide by the 75% - 10% - 15% proportion.

4.1. Protest news data

The news classification task data consists of local India and China news articles in English language. This data set is borrowed from CLEF-2019 Lab ProtestNews [3]. Train, validation, and test splits are provided by organizers. The news data is specifically a data annotated as to whether it is about a protest event. As illustrated in Table 4.1, the India data is imbalanced with 22% protest class, the China data is even more imbalanced with 5% protest class.

- Local news from India: A news data in English comprising of news texts gathered from different sources from India which are Times of India, New Indian Express, The Indian Express, and The Hindu.
- Local news from China: A news data set in English. comprising of news texts of People’s Daily, and South China Morning Post.

4.1.1. Challenges of political context

In previous work, It is seen that the classification of contentious political events could be confusing to even domain experts and the inter-annotator agreement could be surprisingly low. That confusion mostly comes from the ambiguity in political terms. How a political event could be interpreted can highly depend on local culture, language usage, time, space and actors. Adding the style and biases of the teller, author of news text, a single annotator may not be completely sure of herself, let alone agreeing with fellow annotators.

Members of the Communist Party of India (Marxist) staged a **protest** here on Thursday **demanding** the arrest of the remaining accused in the last month’s assault on party-goers at the Morning Mist Homestay in Padil and filing of cases under the **Goonda Act** against them. The protest meeting was preceded by a rally from Town Hall to ...

Figure 4.1. India news sample.

Police classed as criminal an explosion that killed a **car** driver in Wuhan yesterday - the second lethal vehicle **explosion** in the central city in nearly three months, state media said. Xinhua reported a black car belonging to a Bank of China branch in the city exploded and burst into flames shortly before **mid-day** as it was being driven near the junction of Qianjin 4th Road and Zizhi Street

...It was not clear if the explosion was related to the bank or a **protest** of the recent ban on direct sales by the Government. It was reported that many sales agents in Wuhan had **protested** against the ban. Another unconfirmed report said the explosion might have been the act of laid-off workers.

Figure 4.2. China news sample.

Within the context of contentious politics, “protest” can be very broadly defined as engaging in a political dissent via numerous actions such as demonstrating for rights, rallying for political change, conducting a hunger strike, boycotting rights, and so forth.

4.1.2. Local news data

Political events are strongly connected to their local context. Concerning PC, it should be remembered that protest notions might manifest through different kinds of actions in different cultures. Figure 4.1, the news mentions a protest activity as “Goonda act”, which is a term used in the Indian subcontinent for a hired criminal. In this sense, analyzing local data of many countries can be useful and mostly becomes a necessity to converge to a realistic model of what protest means both globally and locally.

In this study, ELMo and DistilBERT pretrained on large global and diverse data encounters with the local news data from two countries.

data subset	size	protest ratio	protest count
Ntrain	3430	0.22	754
Ndev	457	0.22	100
Ntest	687	0.22	151
Ctest	1800	0.05	90

Table 4.1. Protest - data statistics. Ntrain: Training split of India news articles. Ndev: Development split of India news articles. Ntest: Test split of India news articles. Ctest: China news articles as the cross-context test data.

4.1.3. Long text

The protest news data set consists of fairly long samples with on average 300 tokens on average. This may affect the model performance in two different ways: A model may fail to learn long term relationships within the text. Or a model simply may not be able to utilize the whole text due to memory issues. In this case, very important parts of the data might be lost. For example, the news sample in Figure 4.2 was indeed falsely labeled as “non-protest” by one of the models as the part containing the “protest” keyword was clipped.

4.1.4. Small data

Contextual language representations are known to have the potential to substantially reduce the required training data size to create satisfactory models via task-specific fine-tuning on small data. As illustrated in Table 4.1. the protest news data is also fairly a small one with the number of training samples less than 10000. The average number of tokens is around 300. Here, “token” is used as a generic term for a unit output of a sequence tokenization process.

4.1.5. Data preparation

The data preparation process realizes a state-of-the-art semi-automatic pipeline. First, data is randomly sampled from various news sources, and then it is manually annotated by graduate students in the fields related to politics and sociology. A new annotation manual is created based on prominent event annotation guidelines such as ACE [49] and CAMEO codebook [50], and applied to each data set in the corpus to prevent annotation style ambiguities in error analysis. A supervisor maintains the annotation guideline. The data is annotated in a semi-supervised manner as following: First, students manually annotate by working in pairs, each member of the pairs annotate the same document set on their own. Then the supervisor manually spot-checks 10% of the agreed annotations and resolves the inter-annotator disagreements. Then a semi-supervised quality check is performed by training an ML model using 90% of the data as training and validation sets. 10% of the data as the test set. Training and testing are repeated 10 times. Then the errors of the ML model are manually checked.

Using active learning, candidate positive samples are created as follows: Three separate classifiers are trained. If one of the classifiers predicts a document sample as positive, it is sent to the annotation pipeline. This filtering process runs with 70% precision and 97% recall. By this procedure, it is aimed at building a semi-supervised validation loop to obtain as many relevant documents as possible, without compromise much from precision. It is seen that this technique is much more beneficial to reach a higher recall of relevant documents than a random sampling of a huge corpus with numerous news topics. Note that for this specific task of protest news collection, recall is a bit more important than precision, as detecting as many relevant articles as possible among articles about numerous other categories is crucial to extract sufficient information to test the hypothesis of the socio-political study. Moreover, recall is critical when creating a gold standard data set.

The China data is used as a cross-context test set for models trained at India data. China data is in no way used during training to abide by Protest news Shared Task’s rules for comparability of results with the shared task outcomes.

4.2. Sentiment analysis data

In the second task, Movie Reviews [46] and customer reviews [47] data are used. Both data are annotated binary as positive or negative comments. Both data are sentence-level and rather short compared to the protest news data with an average of 20 tokens as illustrated in Table 4.3. The MR data is class-balanced. There are no predefined training, development, and test splits of both MR and the CR data. Other work using this data generally applies 10-fold cross-validation to these data sets. But this prolongs the hyper-parameter tuning phase to a great extent. Due to time restrictions, a custom split of MR data is created with 75% training - 10% development - 15% test proportions. CR data is used as the cross-context test set as is.

data	examples	label
MR	“Too slow for a younger crowd , too shallow for an older one.”	neg
CR	“We tried it out christmas night and it worked great .”	pos

Table 4.2. Sentiment data samples.

data subset	size	positive ratio	avg len	stdev
Ntrain	7974	0.5	21	9.44
Ndev	1088	0.5	21	9.3
Ntest	1600	0.5	20	9.34
Ctest	3771	0.64	20	11.71

Table 4.3. Sentiment - data statistics. Ntrain: Training split of MR data set. Ndev: Development split of MR data set. Ntest: Test split of MR data set. Ctest: CR data set as the cross-context test data.

5. EXPERIMENTAL SETUP

5.1. Environment setup

The classifiers are implemented in Python programming language using the PyTorch library [51]. The training is done on a single V100 NVIDIA GPU with 16 GB RAM.

5.2. ELMo

ELMo [5] is a deep context-dependent representation learned from the internal states of a deep BiLM that is acquired by the joint training of two LSTM layers on both directions. ELMo obtained state-of-the-art task-specific supervised models in six different NLP tasks, including sequence classification. It is shown that ELMo’s every BiLM layer represents a different type of information, together capturing syntax and disambiguating semantics.

ELMo is pretrained for BiLM objective on One Billion Words Benchmark composed of nearly 30 million monolingual sentences. ELMo word embeddings are created using two BiLM layers and make use of character convolutions, which makes it robust to out-of-vocabulary tokens unseen in training.

This study makes use of the original ELMo model with 2 layer bidirectional LSTM layers with 4096 units and 512-dimensional projections, with a total of 93.6 million parameters. ELMo’s hidden LSTM layers are weighted averaged (scalar-mix method), which is the default combination technique of ELMo, and then fed into the classifier layers.

5.3. DistilBERT

DistilBERT [8] is created by applying knowledge distillation to BERT, specifically the `bert-base-uncased` model, to create a lighter and faster version of BERT for the benefit of under constraint training budgets. It is 40% smaller and 60% faster than the respective BERT model while attaining 97% of BERT’s performance on 6 of 12 downstream tasks. Only the MLM is used as the pretraining objective, omitting BERT’s other objective Next Sentence Prediction. In this study, DistilBERT’s last four hidden layers are simply averaged and fed into the classifier layers, which is a suggested usage of BERT for text classification tasks.

In this study, `distilbert-base-uncased` [52] with 66 million parameters is compared to the original ELMo model with 93.6 million parameters [53]. Note that while the former is case-insensitive, the latter is case-sensitive.

5.4. Baseline models

Optimized Linear SVM (LSVM) and Multinomial Naive Bayes (MNB) scores are reported as baselines [54]. LSVM takes the input as tf-idf (term frequency - inverse document frequency) vectors, whereas MNB as a matrix of token counts. It is important to see how much cheaper, traditional ML algorithms perform compared to heavily pretrained large contextual networks, to understand if the overhead of the models is worth to undertake.

5.5. Classifiers and training schedule

The classifier architectures are kept simple to focus on what information can be easily extracted from the models. First, a 2-layer FFNN with 512 hidden units is used. Then, to better understand the effect of adding task-trained contextualization, a 2-layer BiLSTM with 512 hidden unites is added before the linear output layer. The default maximum sequence length is 256 tokens for PC, 60 tokens for CA. ELMo gets that many full tokens, whereas DistilBERT gets that many WordPiece outputs.

Figure 5.1. Experimental setup.

The classifiers are trained for 10 epochs with Adam optimizer [55] using early stopping with the patience of 3 epochs. train for 50 epochs, using early stopping with the patience of 3 epochs on the development set F-score. During training, the best model is checkpointed regarding the development set F-score. Then the checkpoints are evaluated on the test data. This procedure is repeated for each classifier with 5 random seeds and the average scores are reported. In SA, for the baseline models (MNB and LSVM) the development data is included in the training data after hyperparameter tuning to make use of more data.

Except for DistilBERT, the sequences are tokenized by Spacy’s `en-core-web-sm` tokenizer [56]. DistilBERT uses WordPiece tokenization [57] The first 256 tokens per sample of the protest news data and first 60 tokens per sample of the MR and CR data are given as input to the classifiers. Note that the usage of two different tokenizers causes a mismatch between the input of DistilBERT and other models. But WordPiece tokenization is preferred to be used as it is the default tokenizer of DistilBERT.

5.6. Experiments

The main focus of this study is to acquire an idea of the robustness quality of ELMo and DistilBERT under the usage of cross-context test data (See Figure 5.1). Observing both null and cross-context performance side-by-side helps understand cross-

context robustness more easily. Therefore, all experiments report both null and cross-context results for each task. Each experiment focuses on a particular variation on the classifier architecture that possibly affects the results in its way.

- Experiment 1: Frozen embeddings: Both contextual word embeddings are used as fixed word vectors and fed into FFNN.
- Experiment 2: Fine-tuned embedding: ELMo and DistilBERT are fine-tuned to the training data sets together with the FFNN classifier.
- Experiment 3: Using BiLSTM: Both models are kept frozen, but this time paired with a BiLSTM instead of an FFNN.
- Experiment 4: Fine-tuning + BiLSTM: ELMo and DistilBERT are compared under the combined effect of fine-tuning contextual embeddings and pairing with a 2-layer BiLSTM.

5.7. Evaluation criteria

The protest news data is highly imbalanced regarding the class frequencies (negative class is dominant). Macro-averaging provides a more robust evaluation for class-imbalanced data. On the other hand, macro-averaging and micro-averaging are equivalent in the case of class-balanced data sets, such as the MR data. Macro averaged F-score ($\beta = 1$) is used as the primary evaluation metric in both tasks. To capture cross-context robustness better, also as an additional metric, the F-score drop between null and cross-context is tracked in percentages. That is, for example, if model x null context F-score is f_n and the cross-context setting F-score is f_c , then the drop in F-score is calculated as $(f_n - c_n)/f_n$. Since PC data is imbalanced, positive class scores are also recorded in PC. Accuracy in SA is additionally reported for compatibility with the previous work in Section A as well as standard deviations.

So three evaluation scores are recorded for each model for both tasks:

- F-score in the null context (Ntest).
- F-score in the cross-context (Ctest).

- The F-score drop between null and cross-context tracked in percentages (Drop).

The other metrics reported for PC;

- F-score for positive (protest) class in null context (Npos).
- F-score for positive class in cross-context (Cpos).
- The F-score drop for positive class between null and cross-context tracked in percentages (Drop pos).

5.8. Hyper-parameter tuning

The dropout rate of the classifier (FFNN or BiLSTM), learning rate, learning rate decay, L2 norm, and whether to use ReLU or not, are the hyper-parameters that were tuned for each model. Hyper-parameter space to traverse is illustrated in Table 5.1 that is determined within the range of the hyper-parameter values settled in related work [5] [6] [8] [25] [27] [28]. Hyper-parameters of ELMo and DistilBERT are kept unchanged.

hyper-parameter	range
learning rate	5e-5, 1e-3, 1e-1
learning rate decay	0, 0.5
dropout	0, 0.25, 0.5
L2	0, 0.01
Use ReLu?	True, False

Table 5.1. Hyper-parameter space.

Hyper-parameters of each distinct model is optimized on the validation data with The Tree-structured Parzen Estimator (TPE) algorithm [58]. The implementation of the algorithm is provided by the hyperopt package [59]. TPE mainly traverses a hyper-parameter space by pruning it effectively to optimize a predefined metric on the evaluation subset of the data. TPE is shown to converge faster to the best hyper-

parameters than random or grid search [58].

For SA, cross-validated data required nested cross-validation during hyper-parameter tuning, which can get out of hand if hyper-parameter space contains more than a couple of points. But in this study, the hyper-parameter space contains 72 different combinations of points for the neural networks. This number is reduced to 25 with a bayesian-based tuning technique. This process has to be done for 8 different models (4 ELMo, 4 DistilBERT) for SA. There was not much time left for that kind of tuning. Therefore, a custom stratified training, development, and test splits of the MR data is created and these splits are used throughout the experiments.

For SA, cross-validated data required nested cross-validation during hyper-parameter tuning, which can get out of hand if hyper-parameter space contains more than a couple of points. But in this study, the hyper-parameter space contains 72 different configurations of points. Number of data points visited during hyper-parameter tuning is indeed reduced to 25 with a bayesian-based tuning technique, but 25 is still an unfeasible number considering 8 this process has to be done for 8 different models (4 ELMo, 4 DistilBERT). There was not much time left for that kind of tuning. Therefore, I created custom and stratified training, development, and test splits of the MR data and used them throughout the experiments.

The hyper-parameter tuning for the baselines was straightforward, for there were a few possible hyper-parameters to be tuned. For MNB, “alpha” the additive smoothing parameter, and the choice of whether to learn class prior probabilities or not are tuned. For LSVM, the loss function type as “hinge” or “squared hinge”, the tolerance for stopping criteria, and “C” the regularization parameter are tuned.

5.9. Statistical tests

Two statistical tests are performed on ELMo and DistilBERT results: randomization test and McNemar’s test. The former checks if the two models significantly differ in terms of scores. The latter checks if they differ in their failures in predicting

the same samples.

5.9.1. Randomization test

The first statistical test is the randomization (permutation) test [60], which is a technique to see if the difference between the performance of two models on some metric is significant or happened by chance. Randomization test is favorable in NLP problems over other widely used statistical test techniques such as the t-test. Because, unlike the t-test, the randomization test does not assume any distribution over data. And it also does not assume independence between predictions of two models.

Randomization test is performed by calculating p-values for all combinations of predictions obtained by training with different seeds. For example, when two models of ELMo and DistilBERT are compared, 25 different p-values are produced by using 25 different pairs of 5 ELMo and 5 DistilBERT outcomes. The harmonic mean of these p-values is used as the ultimate statistic of the test to smooth the disproportional effect of large p-values in arithmetic mean.

The harmonic mean of a series equals to zero if the series contains any zero value. For more realistic evaluation, the harmonic mean of non-zero p-values is also reported. But zero values should not be entirely ignored since their existence points out that rejection of the null hypothesis is indeed very much probable.

As a widely used technique, the matched-pair t-test is not an equally suitable option for two reasons: Firstly, the matched-pair t-test assumes a Gaussian distribution over the statistical value it uses. Moreover, the matched-pair t-test is effective when comparing recall, but not as effective when comparing precision and F-score. This is because precision and F-score are more complicated and non-linear functions of random variables than recall [60].

5.9.2. McNemar's test

The other statistical test applied here is McNemar's test which is proved to have low Type I error [61]. Unlike the randomization test, McNemar's test is interested in how the modes label specific test instances. McNemar's test aims at measuring the level of discrepancy between the models' failures. The overall p-value for a single test is calculated in the same way as the randomization test (taking harmonic mean).

6. EXPERIMENT RESULTS

In this section, ELMo and DistilBERT are compared using various classification architectures on two text classification tasks in a cross-context.

6.1. Comparing ELMo and DistilBERT

This section consists of direct comparison of ELMo and DistilBERT by isolating them under different circumstances enabled by varying the training style (freeze or fine-tune embeddings), and the classifier architecture (adding BiLSTM to the classifier).

As a side note, fine-tuned ELMo does not fit into a single GPU with 256 tokens per input sample. This issue is encountered in PC, for news inputs consist of multiple sentences. In this case, when fine-tuned, ELMo could manage up to 150 tokens per input. For a fair comparison, DistilBERT is also fine-tuned with 150 tokens. But since DistilBERT can handle 256 tokens per input, DistilBERT results on 256 tokens per input are also reported.

6.1.1. Experiment 1: Frozen embeddings

In the first experiment, both contextual word embeddings are used as fixed word vectors without further fine-tuning on the two classification tasks and fed into FFNN. In this sense, here what is compared is the generalization capacity of the models coming only from the pretraining phase.

Table 6.1 and 6.2 shows that frozen DistilBERT is on par with or exceeding frozen ELMo in the null context (India and MR test sets). On the other hand, as illustrated in the “Drop” column on the Table 6.1, DistilBERT outperforms ELMo in the cross-contexts with a smaller “Drop” score in both tasks.

task	model	Ntest	Npos	Ctest	Cpos	Test avg	Pos avg	Drop	Pos Drop
PC	ELMo 256	83.6	74.8	75.2	52.6	79.4	63.7	10	29.6
PC	DistilBERT 256	83.8	75	76.8	56	80.3	65.5	8.2	25.2

Table 6.1. PC results of frozen ELMo and DistilBERT combined with FFNN.

task	model	Ntest	Ctest	Test avg	Drop
SA	ELMo 60	78	63.6	70.8	18.4
SA	DistilBERT 60	79	66.8	72.9	15.4

Table 6.2. SA results of frozen ELMo and DistilBERT combined with FFNN.

6.1.2. Experiment 2: Fine-tuned embeddings

In the second part of the experiments, ELMo and DistilBERT are fine-tuned on the training data sets together with the FFNN classifier.

For PC, fine-tuned ELMo, does not fit into a single GPU with 256 tokens per input sample. This issue is encountered in PC, for news inputs consist of multiple sentences. In this case, ELMo could manage up to 150 tokens per input. For a fair comparison, DistilBERT is trained twice, first with 150 tokens of input, and then as a separate model, with 256 tokens of input. The maximum sequence limit does not become an issue for SA, as the sentiment data is sentence-level and much shorter (300 tokens vs. 20 tokens on average).

task	model	Ntest	Npos	Ctest	Cpos	Test avg	Pos avg	Drop	Pos Drop
PC	ELMo ft 150	83	74	72.2	47	77.6	60.5	12.8	36.4
PC	DistilBERT ft 150	80	69	71	45.6	75.5	57.3	11	33.8
PC	DistilBERT ft 256	83.2	74.6	76.4	55.4	79.8	65	8.2	25.6

Table 6.3. PC results of fine-tuned ELMo and DistilBERT combined with FFNN.

task	model	Ntest	Ctest	Test avg	Drop
SA	ELMo ft 60	76.2	69	72.6	9.6
SA	DistilBERT ft 60	79	68	73.5	14.2

Table 6.4. SA results of fine-tuned ELMo and DistilBERT combined with FFNN.

As illustrated in Table 6.3, when finetuned, ELMo outperforms DistilBERT when the context is restricted to 150 tokens, but falls behind in 256 tokens especially in cross-context. Table 6.4 shows that DistilBERT outperforms ELMo in the null context, but falls behind in the cross-context. This indicates that in SA, fine-tuning made ELMo more robust to context change in the test set.

Here it should be noted that DistilBERT does not use as many full tokens as Elmo since DistilBERT adopts WordPiece tokenization on default. Given this situation, providing DistilBERT as many full tokens would have allowed a fairer comparison. Though in this study, this modification is not done to minimize the effect of any customization upon functions of ELMo and DistilBERT’s libraries, including tokenization style.

6.1.3. Experiment 3: External contextualization via BiLSTM

In this experiment, both models are kept frozen, but this time paired with a BiLSTM instead of an FFNN. BiLSTM adds contextualization on the focused task, thus it is expected to improve results.

task	model	Ntest	Npos	Ctest	Cpos	Test avg	Pos avg	Drop	Pos Drop
PC	ELMo + BiLSTM 256	81.6	72.2	72.4	47.6	77	59.9	11.2	34
PC	DistilBERT + BiLSTM 256	84.2	76.4	78.4	59	81.3	67.7	7	23

Table 6.5. PC results of frozen ELMo and DistilBERT combined with BiLSTM.

task	model	Ntest	Ctest	Test avg	Drop
SA	ELMo + BiLSTM 60	79	67	73	15.2
SA	DistilBERT + BiLSTM 60	80	70.2	75.1	12.4

Table 6.6. SA results of frozen ELMo and DistilBERT combined with BiLSTM.

As the Tables 6.5 and 6.6 illustrate, in both tasks DistilBERT outperforms ELMo when paired with a 2-layer BiLSTM. The gap is more visible in the cross-context performance: As shown in Table 6.5, DistilBERT outperforms ELMo 6 points with a 78.4 Ctest F-score.

6.1.4. Experiment 4: Combine fine-tuning with BiLSTM

In this experiment, ELMo and DistilBERT are compared under the combined effect of fine-tuning and the usage of 2-layer BiLSTM. Note that, in PC, ELMo could handle at most 150 tokens per input. Therefore, the comparison is done under that much of a sequence length.

task	model	Ntest	Npos	Ctest	Cpos	Test avg	Pos avg	Drop	Pos Drop
PC	ELMo ft + BiLSTM 150	82	72.4	72	46.6	77	59.5	12.2	35.6
PC	DistilBERT ft + BiLSTM 150	81.8	71.8	72.2	47.6	77	59.7	11.8	33.6

Table 6.7. PC results of fine-tuned ELMo and DistilBERT combined with BiLSTM.

task	model	Ntest	Ctest	Test avg	Drop
SA	ELMo ft + BiLSTM 60	78.2	67.4	72.8	13.8
SA	DistilBERT ft + BiLSTM 60	80	70.2	75.1	12.4

Table 6.8. SA results of fine-tuned ELMo and DistilBERT combined with BiLSTM.

As a reminder, in Experiment 2, DistilBERT was underperforming on sequences of length 150 in PC. Now, as illustrated in Table 6.7 DistilBERT catches up with ELMo. This indicates that DistilBERT benefits from BiLSTM. Again, if Experiment

2 is recalled, DistilBERT was occasionally underperforming ELMo in SA. But now the results in Table 6.8 are in favor of DistilBERT. This indicates BiLSTM enabled DistilBERT to surpass ELMo results.

6.1.5. Comparison to baselines

For fairness, both ELMo’s and DistilBERT’s best and worst-performing configurations are compared to the hyper-parameter-tuned MNB and LSVM baselines. The best performing models are indicated with “highest”, the worst-performing with “lowest” on Table 6.9 and 6.10. Two models are reported as the “highest” of ELMo in SA as one owns better “Drop” scores.

task	model	Ntest	Npos	Ctest	Cpos	Test avg	Pos avg	Drop	Pos Drop
PC	LSVM 256	78	64	63	28	70.5	46	19	56
PC	MNB 256	82	72	71	46	76.5	59	13	36
PC	ELMo + BiLSTM 256 (lowest)	81.6	72.2	72.4	47.6	77	59.9	11.2	34
PC	ELMo 256 (highest)	83.6	74.8	75.2	52.6	79.4	63.7	10	29.6
PC	DistilBERT ft 256 (lowest)	83.2	74.6	76.4	55.4	79.8	65	8.2	25.6
PC	DistilBERT 256 (highest)	83.8	75	76.8	56	80.3	65.5	8.2	25.2

Table 6.9. PC - Comparison with three baselines.

task	model	Ntest	Ctest	Test avg	Drop
SA	MNB 60	75	55	65	27
SA	Linear SVM 60	77	62	69.5	19
SA	ELMo 60 (lowest)	78	63.6	64	18.4
SA	ELMo ft 60 (highest 1)	76.2	69	69.2	9.6
SA	ELMo + BiLSTM 60 (highest 2)	79	67	67	15.2
SA	DistilBERT 60 (lowest)	79	66.8	67	15.4
SA	DistilBERT ft + BiLSTM 60 (highest)	80	70.2	70.2	12.4

Table 6.10. SA - comparison with the baselines.

Table 6.9 demonstrates that in PC, while LSVM cannot catch up with any model,

MNB performs fairly on par with ELMo’s worst-performing model. Apart from that, MNB is effectively surpassed by the best of ELMo and DistilBERT in all tracks. As shown in Table 6.10, in SA, MNB is inferior to all models. The results of LSVM and ELMo’s lowest are close to each other. But the best of ELMo and all variants of DistilBERT surpass the LSVM baseline with an apparent gap in the cross-context robustness.

It is also visible in the Tables 6.9 and 6.10 that DistilBERT outperforms ELMo on both tasks with both of its worst-performing and best-performing variants. This can be viewed as an indicator of the possible superiority if DistilBERT.

6.1.6. Average results

To view the experiment from a wider perspective, the models are also compared under the arithmetic average of all variations. For fairness, only “common” model configurations are used to find averages. That is, DistilBERT’s fine-tuned models making use of 256 length input are excluded from the computation because there is no equivalent model on the ELMo side.

As Table 6.11 displays, ELMo is found to be superior to DistilBERT on average when both use only 150 tokens of protest news input. But as illustrated in Table 6.12, in SA when full context is available DistilBERT performs better regardless of short sequence length. On average, for both PC and SA, DistilBERT outperforms ELMo. This can be seen as yet another indicator of DistilBERT’s potential superiority.

task	average	Ntest	Npos	Ctest	Cpos	Test avg	Pos avg	Drop	Pos Drop
PC	ELMo 150	81.95	72.15	73.25	49	77.6	60.58	10.55	31.9
PC	DistilBERT 150	80.95	70.7	72.8	48.6	76.88	59.65	10	31.25
PC	ELMo	82.17	72.6	73.43	49.37	77.8	60.98	10.57	31.87
PC	DistilBERT (common)	82.87	74.03	76.13	54.83	79.5	64.43	8.1	26.03

Table 6.11. PC - average results of ELMo and DistilBERT.

task	model	Ntest	Ctest	Test avg	Drop
SA	ELMo	77.85	66.75	72.3	14.25
SA	DistilBERT	79.5	68.8	74.15	13.6

Table 6.12. SA - average results of ELMo and DistilBERT.

6.1.7. Training time and model size

Training time, inference time, and model size should be within a reasonable range especially in real-life scenarios. But in research studies as well it becomes important. For example, the whole pipeline from hyper-parameter tuning to inference would be re-iterated when a new data set arrives. In this section, DistilBERT and ELMo are compared in terms of the training and inference time, as well as the model size.

Training times and model sizes are compared by averaging all model configurations common to ELMo and DistilBERT. Training and inference time are summed up to a single number. According to Table 6.13, DistilBERT is 30% smaller and 80% faster than ELMo on the average of both tasks. In terms of classifier size (excluding embeddings) DistilBERT is 13% smaller than ELMo. On the other hand, MNB and LSVM are far cheaper than DistilBERT in size and speed by being 99% smaller and 96% faster.

task	model	embedding size (MB)	model size (MB)	train time (secs)
PC	MNB	-	1.1	12
PC	ELMo	358	75.55	1684
PC	DistilBERT (common)	254	65.8	316
PC	LSVM	-	0.133	10
SA	ELMo	358	75.55	979
SA	DistilBERT	254	65.8	230

Table 6.13. Average training time and model size of ELMo and DistilBERT.

6.2. Statistical tests

In the previous section, it was observed that on average DistilBERT outperforms ELMo. But the gap between ELMo’s and DistilBERT’s scores is not very obvious, especially in null-context. So it is worth to see if the overall superiority of DistilBERT over ELMo is indeed significant.

In this section, randomization and McNemar’s tests are realized on the best performing variants of the models according to Table 6.9 and 6.10. For SA, “ELMo + BiLSTM 60 (highest 2)” is picked as the best ELMo variant on average test scores.

The main focus is to compare ELMo and DistilBERT to each other, and also see if traditional ML methods can compete with contextual embeddings at all. Here ELMo is compared to the baselines since the gap between ELMo and the baselines was relatively smaller in the experiments. That is, three different pairings are formed: ELMo-DistilBERT, ELMo-MNB, and ELMo-SVM.

6.2.1. Randomization test

Two-tailed and one-tailed tests are conducted under the significance level of $\alpha = 0.05$. The null hypothesis is rejected when $p < 0.025$ in two-tailed, $p < 0.05$ in one-tailed tests. The harmonic mean of non-zero p-values is reported along with zero harmonic means, separated by a / symbol (find details in Section 5).

First, two-tailed randomization tests are realized between the selected models in the relevant tasks. The null hypothesis is that there is no significant difference between the scores of the compared models.

compared models	task	Ntest	Ntest pos	Ctest	Ctest pos	Drop	Drop pos
ELMo-DistilBERT	PC	0.43	0/0.01	0.38	0/0.007	0.59	0/0.005
ELMo-MNB	PC	0.46	0.083	0.34	0/0.01	0.75	0/0.11

Table 6.14. PC two-tailed randomization test p-value results on the best performing model variations of ELMo, DistilBERT, and MNB.

compared models	task	Ntest	Ctest	Drop
ELMo-DistilBERT	SA	0.033	0/0.008	0.06
ELMo-LSVM	SA	0.17	0	0/0.019

Table 6.15. SA - two-tailed randomization test p-value results on the best performing model variations of ELMo, DistilBERT, and LSVM.

As the Tables 6.14 and 6.15 both illustrate, the test results point out to a significant difference between DistilBERT and ELMo in cross-context. Similarly, it seems ELMo and the baselines differ in cross-context robustness. But the test failed to reject that ELMo and the baselines perform similarly in the null context.

The next step is the one-tailed randomization test. The one-tailed test is only meaningful when the null hypothesis is rejected in the two-tailed test. Therefore, the one-tailed test is only applied to the criteria below:

- “Ctest” scores of DistilBERT and ELMo.
- “Drop” scores of DistilBERT and ELMo.
- “Ctest” scores of ELMo and the baselines.

compared models	task	Ctest	Ctest pos	Drop	Drop pos
ELMo-DistilBERT	PC	0.2	0/0.004	0.31	0/0.006
ELMo-MNB	PC	0.19	0/0.009	0.36	0/0.056

Table 6.16. PC - One-tailed randomization test p-value results on the best performing model variations of ELMo, DistilBERT, and MNB.

compared models	task	Ctest	Ctest pos	Drop	Drop pos
ELMo-DistilBERT	SA	0/0.017	0/0.047	0.02/0.02	0/0.02
ELMo-LSVM	SA	0/0	0/0	0.003/0.003	0/0.003

Table 6.17. SA - One-tailed randomization test p-value results on the best performing model variations of ELMo, DistilBERT, and LSVM.

As shown in the Tables 6.16 and 6.17, DistilBERT is more robust to cross-context than ELMo in PC positive class and both classes of SA. ELMo is more robust to cross-context than MNB in PC positive class and than LSVM in both classes of SA.

6.2.2. McNemar’s test

McNemar’s test enables to see if the models differ in their failures. The null hypothesis claims they do not. Predefined upper bound for p-value is 0.05 to reject the null hypothesis.

As shown in the Tables 6.18 and 6.19, ELMo and DistilBERT significantly differ from each other in positive class and cross-context predictions. ELMo differs from both baselines in cross-context but no significant difference could be detected in the null context.

compared models	task	Ntest	Ntest pos	Ctest	Ctest pos
ELMo-DistilBERT	PC	0.25	2.30E-05	0.51	2.80E-06
ELMo-MNB	PC	0.095	0.44	0.08	0.012

Table 6.18. PC - McNemar’s test p-value results on the best performing model variations of ELMo, DistilBERT, and MNB.

compared models	task	Ntest	Ctest
ELMo-DistilBERT	SA	0.029	3.30E-23
ELMo-LSVM	SA	0.16	9.43E-18

Table 6.19. SA - McNemar’s test p-value results on the best performing model variations of ELMo, DistilBERT, and LSVM.

6.3. Effect of external factors

In this section, ELMo and DistilBERT are not directly compared to each other. Instead, the effect of various changes to the models and input is examined on both ELMo and DistilBERT, separately. In this sense, this section aims at answering the questions:

- How does fine-tuning on the target task affect ELMo’s and DistilBERT’s performance?
- How does adding a BiLSTM to the network influence ELMo’s and DistilBERT’s performance?
- How sequence length affects the performance in the PC task?

6.3.1. Effect of fine-tuning

Word embeddings can be fine-tuned, meaning that, its weights can be updated during the learning phase to adapt it more to a specific task at hand. In this section, how the performance is affected by unfreezing the model layers,

Table 6.20 and 6.21 show that fine-tuning slightly degraded DistilBERT’s performance in PC, and barely improved SA scores. So, fine-tuning did not have any significant effect on DistilBERT’s performance in either task.

task	model	Ntest	Npos	Ctest	Cpos	Test avg	Pos avg	Drop	Pos Drop
PC	DistilBERT 256	83.8	75	76.8	56	80.3	65.5	8.2	25.2
PC	DistilBERT ft 256	83.2	74.6	76.4	55.4	79.8	65	8.2	25.6

Table 6.20. PC - Effect of fine-tuning on DistilBERT’s performance.

task	model	Ntest	Ctest	Test avg	Drop
SA	DistilBERT 60	79	66.8	72.9	15.4
SA	DistilBERT ft 60	79	68	73.5	14.2

Table 6.21. SA - Effect of fine-tuning on DistilBERT’s performance.

task	model	Ntest	Npos	Ctest	Cpos	Test avg	Pos avg	Drop	Pos Drop
PC	ELMo 150	81.4	70.8	76.6	55.2	79	63	5.8	21.8
PC	ELMo ft 150	83	74	72.2	47	77.6	60.5	12.8	36.4

Table 6.22. PC - Effect of fine-tuning on ELMos’s performance.

task	model	Ntest	Ctest	Test avg	Drop
SA	ELMo 60	78	63.6	70.8	18.4
Sa	ELMo ft 60	76.2	69	72.6	9.6

Table 6.23. SA - Effect of fine-tuning on ELMos’s performance.

The effect of fine-tuning is more visible on ELMo. But how it affects ELMo does not match between the tasks. As illustrated in the table 6.22, in PC, fine-tuning improved results in the null context (India test data) but degraded the results in the cross-context (China test data). But as Table 6.23 illustrates, the impact is the exact opposite in SA: While scores decrease in the null context (MR test data), it increased in the cross-context (CR test data).

As a more generic observation, fine-tuning does not make the models more robust to the cross-context in PC. On the other hand, in SA, it enhances the cross-context

performance. It is known that unfreezing can cause overfitting on small training data [18]. The occasional drop in the null context performance can be a sign of overfitting.

6.3.2. Effect of BiLSTM

As the Tables 6.24 and 6.25 show, BiLSTM usage consistently helped increase DistilBERT’s performance for both tasks but with rather a small improvement. As illustrated on the Table 6.25 the cross-context gain is most visible when DistilBERT is frozen in SA, with the improvement in the MR test score (see the “Ctest” column) from 66.8 to 70.2 F-score.

task	model	Ntest	Npos	Ctest	Cpos	Test avg	Pos avg	Drop	Pos Drop
PC	DistilBERT 256	83.8	75	76.8	56	80.3	65.5	8.2	25.2
PC	DistilBERT + BiLSTM 256	84.2	76.4	78.4	59	81.3	67.7	7	23
PC	DistilBERT ft 256	83.2	74.6	76.4	55.4	79.8	65	8.2	25.6
PC	DistilBERT ft + BiLSTM 256	84	76.2	77.2	57.4	80.6	66.8	8	24.8

Table 6.24. PC - Effect of BiLSTM usage on DistilBERT’s performance. The models are compared in pairs from top to down.

task	model	Ntest	Ctest	Test avg	Drop
SA	DistilBERT 60	79	66.8	72.9	15.4
SA	DistilBERT + BiLSTM 60	80	70.2	75.1	12.4
SA	DistilBERT ft 60	79	68	73.5	14.2
SA	DistilBERT ft + BiLSTM 60	80	70.2	75.1	12.4

Table 6.25. SA - Effect of BiLSTM usage on DistilBERT’s performance. The models are compared in pairs from top to down.

The effect of BiLSTM is not as consistent on ELMo as it was on DistilBERT. BiLSTM more or less always improved the DistilBERT performance, but there is no such a pattern for ELMo. As illustrated in Table 6.26, BiLSTM usage affects ELMo badly in PC, especially in the cross-context performance of frozen ELMo with drop

from 52.6 to 47.6 F-score. Meanwhile, as Table 6.25 shows, in SA BiLSTM improves cross-context robustness of frozen ELMo, but affects the fine-tuned ELMo negatively.

ELMo’s inner architecture resembles a BiLSTM, but DistilBERT’s doesn’t. That could be one reason that ELMo cannot benefit from additional LSTM contextualization as much as DistilBERT.

task	model	Ntest	Npos	Ctest	Cpos	Test avg	Pos avg	Drop	Pos Drop
PC	ELMo 256	83.6	74.8	75.2	52.6	79.4	63.7	10	29.6
PC	ELMo + BiLSTM 256	81.6	72.2	72.4	47.6	77	59.9	11.2	34
PC	ELMo ft 150	83	74	72.2	47	77.6	60.5	12.8	36.4
PC	ELMo ft + BiLSTM 150	82	72.4	72	46.6	77	59.5	12.2	35.6

Table 6.26. PC - Effect of BiLSTM usage on ELMo’s performance. The models are compared in pairs from top to down.

task	model	Ntest	Ctest	Test avg	Drop
SA	ELMo 60	78	63.6	70.8	18.4
SA	ELMo + BiLSTM 60	79	67	73	15.2
SA	ELMo ft 60	76.2	69	72.6	9.6
SA	ELMo ft + BiLSTM 60	78.2	78.2	72.8	13.8

Table 6.27. SA - Effect of BiLSTM usage on ELMo’s performance. The models are compared in pairs from top to down.

6.3.3. Effect of sequence length

Sequence length is one of the parameters that NLP practitioners should sometimes restrict to a certain level due to limited device memory. In this section, the effect of the sequence length is observed in the PC task. When ELMo is fine-tuned, it cannot handle long sequences (256) in a single GPU. That is why in PC, the input size is decreased down to 150. But in SA, this was not needed thanks to short input length (20 on average).

In PC, as illustrated in Table 6.28, long sequence consistently enhances DistilBERT’s performance. Longer context enabled to learn better both task-specific as well as transferable features.

task	model	Ntest	Npos	Ctest	Cpos	Test avg	Pos avg	Drop	Pos Drop
PC	DistilBERT 150	80.4	70.2	75.4	53	77.9	61.6	6.2	24.8
PC	DistilBERT 256	83.8	75	76.8	56	80.3	65.5	8.2	25.2
PC	DistilBERT ft 150	80	69	71	45.6	75.5	57.3	11	33.8
PC	DistilBERT ft 256	83.2	74.6	76.4	55.4	79.8	65	8.2	25.6
PC	DistilBERT + BiLSTM 150	81.6	71.8	72.6	48.2	77.1	60	11	32.8
PC	DistilBERT + BiLSTM 256	84.2	76.4	78.4	59	81.3	67.7	7	23
PC	DistilBERT ft + BiLSTM 150	81.8	71.8	72.2	47.6	77	59.7	11.8	33.6
PC	DistilBERT ft + BiLSTM 256	84	76.2	77.2	57.4	80.6	66.8	8	24.8

Table 6.28. Effect of maximum sequence length (token-wise) on DistilBERT’s performance. The models are compared in pairs from top to down.

ELMo cannot always benefit from long sequences as opposed to DistilBERT. As shown in the “Drop” column of Table 6.29, long sequences have occasionally a negative effect in the cross-context performance. It is known that a drawback of LSTM is that it is not very successful in learning long-term dependencies in a sequence due to the vanishing gradient phenomena [18]. On the other hand, transformer-based models can handle it with the attention-based technique [17].

task	model	Ntest	Npos	Ctest	Cpos	Test avg	Pos avg	Drop	Pos Drop
PC	ELMo 150	81.4	70.8	76.6	55.2	79	63	5.8	21.8
PC	ELMo 256	83.6	74.8	75.2	52.6	79.4	63.7	10	29.6
PC	ELMo + BiLSTM 150	81.4	71.4	72.2	47.2	76.8	59.3	11.4	33.8
PC	ELMo + BiLSTM 256	81.6	72.2	72.4	47.6	77	59.9	11.2	34

Table 6.29. Effect of maximum sequence length (token-wise) on ELMo’s performance. The models are compared in pairs from top to down.

6.4. New state-of-the-art in CLEF-2019 Lab ProtestNews

If time and resources allow, hyper-parameter tuning can effectively improve results. In this study, combining contextual embeddings with standard shallow neural networks (FFNN and BiLSTM) and applying hyper-parameter tuning helped outperform the prior results in the CLEF-2019 Lab ProtestNews in cross-context while getting comparable results in null context. As shown in Table 6.30, F-score in China test set increased from 65% to 76.8%; “Drop” is diminished from 22% to 8.2%.

Ntest	Ctest	Drop	
Radford et al. [37]	83	65	22
DistilBERT 256	83.8	76.8	8.2

Table 6.30. Comparison with CLEF-2019 Lab ProtestNews results. The prior state-of-the-art is exceeded in cross-context.

7. DISCUSSION

DistilBERT is better at utilizing longer sequences than ELMo. Finetuned ELMo cannot handle as many tokens as DistilBERT can due to excessive RAM usage. This deteriorates ELMo’s performance, especially in the cross-context. Moreover, Finetuning causes ELMo train 1.5X longer, while the effect is negligible in DistilBERT.

One possible reason for DistilBERT’s overall superiority over ELMo might be that transformer-based models can catch long-term dependencies in a sequence input better than LSTM-based models.

One may notice that there is almost always a discrepancy between overall data set statistics and positive class (protest) statistics in PC. For example, DistilBERT almost always outperforms ELMo in positive class statistics while fails to do so in general scores such as Ctest and Drop. This pattern is absent in SA statistics. This phenomenon can be associated with the class imbalance in the protest news data set. At this point, one wonders whether the results would be in favor of DistilBERT if it is not for class-imbalance. This question is left unanswered within the scope of this work.

One remark should be made that since statistical tests are not transitive, no definite conclusions can be drawn on comparing DistilBERT and the baselines. But as mentioned earlier, this was not among the main objectives of the study.

Theoretically, the data sets are big enough to realize statistical tests, but more powerful conclusions could be drawn with larger data.

Adding a BiLSTM to the classifier network, or fine-tuning the pretrained embedding on the training data of the targeted task are two obvious steps for better results in general. But one must be aware that adding more complexity to a neural network or fine-tuning does not necessarily improve results. The real effect of all of these attempts is eventually strictly bounded by the training data and the task itself. The imbalance

between data classes, the noise within the data, the complexity of the classification task, all of these can make a presumably simple binary classification problem a rather complex one.

One interesting observation is that null context performance and cross-context performance do not necessarily grow together. For some specific configurations, when DistilBERT outperformed ELMo in the null context, ELMo happened to outperform DistilBERT in the cross-context or vice versa. Similarly, fine-tuning could improve null context performance but cause a drop in the cross-context performance. Even usage of longer context can cause such an effect. These observations indicate that it is important to check the robustness of a model on multiple dimensions to understand true generalization power.

Recently, it was shown that ELMo and BERT make no significant difference in semantic analysis [27]. Here it is observed that although they are close-by in the null context, DistilBERT is more robust than ELMo in the cross-context in text classification.

The findings of this study are in line with prior work. The fairly comparable scores of ELMo and the traditional baselines in the null context supports the observation of [26] that is, when it comes to contextual embeddings, there is only a small improvement in learning semantics over traditional ML methods. DistilBERT is on par with or exceeding ELMo on a binary text classification task [27]. DistilBERT, as a transformer-based model, is better in capturing long-term dependencies in an input sequence [17]. DistilBERT is lighter than ELMo and has a shorter training time [8].

8. CONCLUSION

In this study, two state-of-the-art contextual language representations, ELMo and DistilBERT, are compared in an extrinsic manner, through two different text classification tasks, namely, PC and SA. In both tasks, two different test data sets are used: one as a subsection of the corpus that the training data comes from, the other is a test set coming from a distinct country and a domain, in news classification and SA, respectively.

The main motive is to contribute to the evaluation space of these two competing contextual language representations by comparing them on the robustness to unseen test data, which is one of the main indicators that tell about generalization capacity. With this respect, the experiments are designed around a cross-context setup. The comparison is done focusing on three different criteria: F-score on the test data (null context), F-score on the cross-context test data, and the amount of F-score degradation in percentages when shifted from null to cross-context.

The models are compared in several environments. First, they are simply used as fixed word vectors when paired with a simple shallow Feed-Forward Neural Network (FFNN). Second, they are fine-tuned on the training data. Third, they are paired with a Bidirectional Long Short Term Memory (BiLSTM). Lastly, they are both fine-tuned and fed into a 2-layer BiLSTM. MNB and LSVM results are also reported as traditional ML model results. For each of these variations, for each model, hyper-parameter tuning is applied. Each variation is trained with the tuned hyper-parameters with 5 different seeds to get the average performance. After the experiments with these variations, two statistical tests, randomization and McNemar’s tests, are performed, to draw more confident conclusions.

This study methodologically differs from the previous work on evaluating the generalizability by using a new socio-political and local news data set other than vigorously utilized data sets. Second, the comparison is persistently performed under

identical conditions and on a cross-context data, without any domain adaptation.

Overall, DistilBERT is found to generalize better than ELMo on the cross-context, in addition to being 30% smaller in embedding size and 80% faster in training time. No significant difference could be detected between ELMo and DistilBERT in the null context. The baselines are outperformed by both models in the cross-context robustness. But baselines could occasionally get comparable results with ELMo in the null context. Also, they are very economic with 99% smaller size and 96% faster training time than DistilBERT.

As a result, when the transfer power of a model is a priority, it is worth to prefer contextual neural models over traditional ML methods despite much longer training times and memory overhead. On the other hand, traditional ML methods might still be preferred as a low-cost option when there is no anticipated discrepancy between training and test data.

9. FUTURE WORK

This study can be enhanced further in various dimensions. As to the implementation dimension, currently, ELMo and DistilBERT tokenize data differently: the former uses Spacy tokenizer, the latter applies WordPiece tokenization. A fairer comparison could be performed by tokenizing the input in same way. One technical discrepancy occurs in how the models' hidden layers are combined to get a token representation. ELMo's hidden LSTM layers are weighted averaged (scalar-mix method), which is the default combination technique of ELMo. On the other hand, DistilBERT's last four hidden layers are simply averaged, which is a suggested usage of BERT, the model DistilBERT is derived from, for text classification tasks. Also, for a more suitable BiLSTM implementation, BiLSTM hidden layer dimension could be set equal to the embedding dimension, instead of fixing to some arbitrary commonly used value such as 512.

Currently, SA is applied to a custom split of the MR data set. K-fold cross-validation could be applied to the SA data. This way, the results would be comparable to the prior work. At least, the results could be averaged over n such custom splits to get a more realistic idea on score distributions.

Inclusion of development set to training set when baselines are trained on the sentiment data gives unfair benefits to the baselines compared to the model models. Excluding development set from training could be a fairer approach.

To better see the effect of contextualization, a non-contextual word representation such as GloVe could be added to the comparisons. Also, a class-balanced document-level data set can be added to the analysis to see the vulnerability of models to class imbalance.

Understanding the data has often been an underestimated part of the whole picture. However, analyzing the data beforehand could help take more realistic decisions

in the succeeding stages. It allows discriminating between the effect of data or task complexity, and the model competency during error analysis. Also, suitable preprocessing steps would improve the results and alleviate the noise in the data.

An extensive error analysis could be done to explain what exactly is learned by the models. This could be done in two main ways: by conventional error analysis methods on predicted development data or focusing on interpreting the black box of the deep neural networks. On the conventional error analysis track, true positive and false negative intersections could be examined manually. On the more innovative track, the hidden state weights of the models could be visualized to understand what the models attend.

Generalization in NLP attracts much attention thanks to two main factors: 1) Most language representations can be pretrained in an unsupervised manner on a large unlabeled data. 2) Once they are pretrained, they can be used as a sane initialization point for many NLP tasks. This way task-specific models can be trained on a little labelled data for a short time. So, currently task-specific training is still bound to labeled data. But actually task-specific training can very much profit from unsupervised learning: 1) Data annotation phase would be shortened and deployment of NLP systems could be faster. 2) With diverse unlabelled data, models could be more robust to different domains. For example, in this study the classifiers could adapt to many different cross-context settings more effectively and much faster. Therefore, unsupervised domain adaptation seems to be a wise direction to take [29].

Also, analysing conflicting information within the same data can help explaining the decision of the models. Confidence scores can also be incorporated into training to interpret the gray area better [62].

Diversity in data is a requirement for models to acquire transferable features of language. But as Bottou et al. [63] highlights, models might learn spurious correlations from a diverse dataset. This phenomena hinders model from acquiring the casual knowledge. To prevent this issue, the subsets of the diverse data set that are coming

from different environments can be incorporated into the training phase in a controlled manner. Bottou et al. [63] proposed a method to minimize the average risk across all environments. It would be curious to see the effect of such an approach in cross-context robustness.

Humans indeed have natural ability to map concepts to practicality. But how it is achieved remains as a dilemma introducing such questions: How the level of abstraction is determined? How is the cost function defined? How are concepts incorporated into general knowledge? How is hierarchy of concepts handled? How is any conflict between definitions handled? What about uncertainty?

To be able to create NLP systems that are robust to the signal complexity and variety human face in real life, such questions should be tackled with. It is curious to think how all this can eventually boil down to modeling the data better. In this path, evaluating the state-of-the-art is of vital importance to find even better data representations. And doing this evaluation in a well-defined and systematic way can accelerate progress by enabling reproducibility and collaboration.

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APPENDIX A: Detailed PC and SA results

model	Ntest	Ntest stdev	Npos	Npos stdev	Ctest	Ctest stdev	Cpos	Cpos stdev	Test avg	Test avg stdev	Pos avg	Pos avg stdev	Drop	Drop stdev	Pos Drop	Pos drop stdev
ELMo 256	83.6	0.55	74.8	0.84	75.2	1.3	52.6	2.7	79.4	0.42	63.7	1.15	10	2.35	29.6	4.16
ELMo 150	81.4	1.34	70.8	2.17	76.6	0.55	55.2	1.1	79	0.87	63	1.54	5.8	1.1	21.8	1.79
ELMo ft 150	83	1	74	2.12	72.2	0.45	47	0.71	77.6	0.42	60.5	0.94	12.8	1.3	36.4	2.61
ELMo + BiLSTM 256	81.6	1.34	72.2	2.17	72.4	2.3	47.6	4.34	77	1.32	59.9	2.51	11.2	3.35	34	6.04
ELMo + BiLSTM 150	81.4	0.89	71.4	1.82	72.2	1.3	47.2	2.77	76.8	0.57	59.3	1.15	11.4	2.3	33.8	4.97
ELMo ft + BiLSTM 150	82	1.22	72.4	2.07	72	1.58	46.6	2.61	77	1.37	59.5	2.29	12.2	0.84	35.6	2.3
DistilBERT 256	83.8	0.84	75	1.87	76.8	1.1	56	2.35	80.3	0.27	65.5	1	8.2	2.28	25.2	4.15
DistilBERT 150	80.4	0.55	70.2	0.45	75.4	0.89	53	2	77.9	0.42	61.6	1.14	6.2	1.64	24.8	2.68
DistilBERT ft 256	83.2	0.84	74.6	1.67	76.4	0.89	55.4	1.82	79.8	0.76	65	1.5	8.2	1.3	25.6	2.19
DistilBERT ft 150	80	1.41	69	3.24	71	2.55	45.6	4.34	75.5	1.17	57.3	2.14	11	4.06	33.8	7.95
DistilBERT BiLSTM 256	84.2	1.79	76.4	3.05	78.4	2.61	59	5.2	81.3	2.11	67.7	3.88	7	1.87	23	5.39
DistilBERT BiLSTM 150	81.6	0.89	71.8	1.3	72.6	0.89	48.2	2.17	77.1	0.82	60	1.62	11	0.71	32.8	2.39
DistilBERT ft + BiLSTM 256	84	1.58	76.2	2.59	77.2	1.48	57.4	2.19	80.6	1.52	66.8	2.33	8	0.71	24.8	1.3
DistilBERT ft + BiLSTM 150	81.8	0.84	71.8	1.3	72.2	1.48	47.6	2.88	77	0.94	59.7	1.96	11.8	1.92	33.6	3.36

Table A.1. PC results including standard deviations.

model	Ntest	Ntest stdev	Nacc	Nacc	Ctest	Ctest stdev	Cacc	Cacc stdev	Test avg	Test avg stdev	Acc avg	Acc avg stdev	Drop	Drop avg	Adrop	Adrop avg
ELMo 60	78	0.71	78	0.71	63.6	1.14	64	0.71	70.8	0.76	71	1	18.4	1.14	18	0.71
ELMo ft 60	76.2	0.45	76.2	0.45	69	1.58	69.2	1.48	72.6	0.89	72.7	1	9.6	1.95	9.2	1.79
ELMo + BiLSTM 60	79	0.71	79	0.71	67	2.65	67	2.65	73	1.5	73	2	15.2	3.27	15.2	3.27
ELMo ft + BiLSTM 60	78.2	0.84	78.2	0.84	67.4	1.34	67.6	1.67	72.8	1.04	72.9	1	13.8	0.84	13.4	1.52
DistilBERT 60	79	0.71	79	0.71	66.8	3.96	67	3.54	72.9	2.27	73	2	15.4	4.51	15.2	4.09
DistilBERT ft 60	79	0.71	79	0.71	68	1.22	68	1.22	73.5	0.5	73.5	1	14.2	2.17	14.2	2.17
DistilBERT + BiLSTM 60	80	1	80	1	70.2	2.28	70.2	2.28	75.1	1.64	75.1	2	12.4	1.82	12.4	1.82
DistilBERT ft + BiLSTM 60	80	1	80	1	70.2	2.28	70.2	2.28	75.1	1.64	75.1	2	12.4	1.82	12.4	1.82

Table A.2. SA results including standard deviations. Macc: Accuracy on MR. Cacc: Accuracy on CR. Acc avg: Acc avg Average of null and cross-context accuracies. Adrop: “Drop” score between null and cross-context accuracies.

APPENDIX B: Hyper-parameter tuning results

task	model	opt best train F-score	opt best dev F-score	opt best epoch no	opt time (hrs:mins)	drop	l2	lr rate	lr decay	relu
PC	ELMo 256	90	87	9	6:26	0.25	0	1e-3	0.5	TRUE
PC	ELMo 150	81	87	5	4:11	0	0.01	1e-3	0.5	TRUE
PC	ELMo ft 150	91	87	9	9:21	0	0	1e-3	0	TRUE
PC	ELMo + BiLSTM 256	84	84	7	8:37	0	0	5e-5	0.5	TRUE
PC	ELMo + BiLSTM 150	89	86	9	4:11	0.5	0.01	1e-3	0	FALSE
PC	ELMo ft + BiLSTM 150	86	87	5	9:03	0	0.01	1e-3	0.5	FALSE
PC	DistilBERT 256	87	87	8	1:49	0	0	1e-3	0	TRUE
PC	DistilBERT 150	83	85	2	1:05	0	0	1e-3	0	TRUE
PC	DistilBERT ft 256	87	87	8	1:52	0.25	0	1e-3	0.5	TRUE
PC	DistilBERT ft 150	78	85	5	1:06	0.25	0	1e-1	0	FALSE
PC	DistilBERT + BiLSTM 256	88	84	7	2:24	0	0.01	1e-3	0	TRUE
PC	DistilBERT + BiLSTM 150	87	85	7	1:27	0.5	0	5e-5	0	FALSE
PC	DistilBERT ft + BiLSTM 256	88	86	6	2:27	0	0.01	1e-3	0	FALSE
PC	DistilBERT ft + BiLSTM 150	87	85	7	1:27	0.5	0	5e-5	0.5	FALSE
SA	ELMo 60	84	80	6	3:56	0	0	1e-3	0.5	TRUE
SA	ELMo ft 60	78	78	6	6:44	0.5	0	1e-3	0	FALSE
SA	ELMo + BiLSTM 60	83	83	2	3:06	0	0	1e-3	0	FALSE
SA	ELMo ft + BiLSTM 60	84	82	2	9:49	0	0	1e-3	0	TRUE
SA	DistilBERT 60	82	79	5	1:10	0	0	1e-3	0.5	TRUE
SA	DistilBERT ft 60	82	79	5	1:32	0.25	0	1e-3	0.5	TRUE
SA	DistilBERT + BiLSTM 60	99	84	8	1:34	0	0	1e-3	0	FALSE
SA	DistilBERT ft + BiLSTM 60	99	84	8	1:08	0	0	1e-3	0	FALSE

Table B.1. Hyper-parameter tuning results.